

Glossary of the article “Citing and referencing habits in Medicine and Social Sciences journals in 2019”

Erika Alves dos Santos – School of Communication and Arts (ECA), Department of Information & Culture (CBD), University of São Paulo (USP), Brazil / Fundação Jorge Duprat Figueiredo de Segurança e Medicina do Trabalho (Fundacentro), Brazil / Digital Humanities Advanced Research Centre (DHARC), Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Italy

Silvio Peroni – Digital Humanities Advanced Research Centre (DHARC), Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Italy / Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata, Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna, Italy

Marcos Luiz Mucheroni – School of Communication and Arts (ECA), Department of Information & Culture (CBD), University of São Paulo (USP), Brazil

One of the findings of this research in the very beginning of its development was the divergences on terminological understandings between Information Science and Computer Science. Citations, bibliographic references, references, among others are some examples of shared terms between these two areas. However, some professionals may have different views on the same term and that situation might configure misunderstandings within the scope of this research considering its multidisciplinary approach. Facing this, it was identified the convenience of describing some technical terms in order to clarify its meaning in the ambit of this discussion.

It is also important to point that some terms may have more than one meaning (and some of them actually do have many), including within other subject areas. For these cases, please keep in mind that this glossary was written considering a librarian’s overview, with some influence of Computer Science.

Article

The smallest part of a periodic publication that, although is itself a distinct entire publication, generally integrates a journal issue. Study of a particular subject, with proper methods and discussion that generally is submitted to an evaluation process and approved by an editorial board prior to publication.

Bibliography

The term bibliography is used for designating a systematic list of sources (e.g. books, articles, and any other press publication) used to write a work (e.g. an article). It usually includes the indication of the sources (publications) consulted and used by an author to formulate and support his own ideas about a topic and also, the ones considered as a convenient (important, useful) background reading for its readers, like a reading suggestion list, (CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008) in the format of bibliographic references.

It is also used to designate a systematic list that gather a compilation of descriptive elements of a group of publications regarding to specific common characteristics shared among them, also in the format of bibliographic references. Bibliographies may be general or specialized and be organized and presented under several approaches: by subject, by chronological order (current, prospective, retrospective), by region, by authorship, or even as a descriptive list of publications targeted to a specific category of readers (CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008).

Bibliography is also used to refer to a set of descriptive metadata, gathered in order to describe a single source of information (e.g., a book, a book chapter, an article etc.), similar than a bibliographic reference. Actually, a bibliography and a bibliographic reference don't differ in a matter of appearance, but in a matter of content and context. Bibliographies and bibliographic references looks very similar, but the first ones refer to the description of a source of information that may be indicated as a reading recommendation or simply an informative note, while bibliographic references refer to the description of a source of information that has been cited in a work.

The term bibliography is ambiguous since it was first used, due to the semantic polyvalence that has been assigned to the term (NAUMIS PEÑA, 2008) and this is not different considering the list of information sources approach, because the term bibliography denotes a pressed source of information, since the radical –bibion refers to books and the prefix –graphy to the writing. These ambiguities are strongly present in the scientific universe and it is common to find the term bibliography used instead of the term bibliographic references, particularly as bibliographic references lists' titles.

For the purposes of this glossary, the term bibliography must be considered as a list of descriptive elements, gathered in bibliographic references format, which stands for a compilation of works suggested as a complimentary content to the content of a work, or a compilation of bibliographic references which indicate the publications consulted by an author for grounding his ideas but not properly cited in the body of the text.

Bibliographic reference

The textual entity within a citing work that identifies a cited work. A bibliographic reference contains some of the elements of the full bibliographic record for the cited work, arranged in a specific format determined by the house style of the citing publication. Some journal house styles require omission of particular elements of the bibliographic record regarded as essential by others, such as the names of all the authors, the title of the article, and the DOI. For a journal article, the bibliographic reference minimally comprises: first author's surname and initials, publication year, abbreviated journal name, volume number, and first and last page numbers. Typically, when the citing work is a scientific journal article, each bibliographic reference is complete in itself and forms a reference list item in the "References" section at the end of the article. In other types of publication, particularly in the humanities, bibliographic references may be contained within footnotes, may be mixed with comments, and may contain pointers, such as "ibid." (abbreviation of the Latin *ibidem*, meaning "the same place") and "op. cit." (abbreviation of the Latin phrase *opere citato*, meaning "in the work cited"), that refer the reader to a previous bibliographic reference from which information needs to be extracted and duplicated to complete the current incomplete bibliographic reference. For this reason, automated parsing of bibliographic references within humanities publications is particularly difficult. Because errors can be introduced when an author creates a bibliographic reference, a published bibliographic reference should not be trusted to be a fully

accurate expression of the information contained within the authoritative bibliographic record for that cited work (PERONI et al., 2015, p. 256-257).

Some publishers use both the terms “references”, “bibliography”, and also “bibliographic references” indistinctly to refer to different things. It suggests a terminological understanding issue that must be clarified and maybe the necessity of adopting a new terminology, once the term “bibliographic” may not be suitable nowadays (see complimentary information at bibliography term definition, above).

In the ambit of this glossary, the term “references” will never be used to refer to bibliographic references (see proper definition for references term below) and must be understood exclusively as a specific kind of reference that refers the reader to an original source of information cited by an author in the text body of a work, and contains the indication of the minimum and indispensable standardized set of precise and detailed descriptive bibliographic metadata for the identification of an information, an entire publication or a specific part of it, a speech, or anything else that may be citable, in order to enable it to be located and retrieved (ABNT, 2018; CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008; ISO, 2010).

Bibliographic references list

The complete descriptive list of bibliographic references of works effectively cited in the main body of a text (work), ordered alphabetically, by the surnames of the cited authors or, numbered consecutively according to the first mention of each publication within the work (the ordination (logical sequence) of bibliographic references in a bibliographic references lists depends on the guidelines of the bibliographic style adopted for writing each work). Formally, the bibliographic references lists should not include bibliographic references of works for which there are any references (mentions or quotations) in the main body of the work.

Bibliographic style

A set of rules, recommendations or guidelines for presenting and formatting academic and scientific works, including bibliographic references. Some bibliographic styles may also contain guidelines on presenting mentions and quotations.

Bibliographic record

A data record containing metadata that fully describes a particular publication and is held in some authoritative information system or library catalogue. A bibliographic record comprises a set of entities defined by the publisher, although the bibliographer or the cataloguer, who usually create bibliographic records, are allowed to include some descriptive information they consider important about the publication being described. A bibliographic record of an article, for example, include but are not restricted to: names of all authors, title of article, journal name, volume number, issue number, first and last page numbers, full publication date, publisher’s name, copyright information, peer-reviewed status, open access status, digital object identifier (DOI) for the article and international standard serial number (ISSN) for the journal (PERONI et al., 2015).

See an example of a bibliographic register within the definition of descriptive element term.

Block quotation

Block quotation (also called long quotation, extract, set-off quotation, or display quotation (NORDQUIST, 2019)) is a quotation (see definition below) that exceed a specific length for which there is no single rule to define the extent limit from which a block quote should be considered as so. Regarding to formatting and presentation rules, block quotations differ from run-in quotations but, once more, there is no a single rule for indicating these differences. Block quotations are typically distinguished visually in the main body of the text (SHOTTON; PERONI, 2015), generally by a left margin indent and a smaller font size than the main text body but, each bibliographic style usually defines its own guidelines for quotations presentation, block quotations included.

Citation

Citation is one of the basic elements of a scientific paper that involves reading, representation, selection, language use, and language understanding behaviours (ZHUGE, 2016), which corresponds to an conceptual link established when a citing work mentions a cited work, or part of it, by including one or more mentions of the cited work content within the body text of that citing work, denoting the bibliographic reference of the cited work at appropriate points (according to the bibliographic style used) through the inclusion of one or more in-text reference pointers and consequently by including the bibliographic reference of the cited work in the bibliographic references list of the citing work. (CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008; PERONI et al., 2015; SHOTTON, 2018).

Citations may be created in the text body of a citing work by the literally reproduction of an extract of the cited work (quotations) or by the basement of a discourse supported (or inspired) on the main idea of the content of the cited work. So, it is proper to consider that mentions are the representation of external information within the text body, and that those mentions (associated to an in-text reference pointer and a corresponding bibliographic reference) constitute the basis that establishes links among works, that is, citations, and supports the citation network.

When indicating a citation, authors generally intend to clarify, base or illustrate a specific approach of a subject; to confirm, deny or make a counterpoint (questioning) to a theory; to highlight similar or opposite expert's opinions about a subject; to reinforce or compare an argument; or to avoid plagiarism and give authorship credits to an statement. Guernsey (1996) complements that the citation is the "mark of honest scholarship". Lanning (2016, p. 22) points that "authors cite sources to show the pedigree of their thinking" (this shows authority), not to plagiarize (that shows accountability), and to allow the reader to find what the author has cited (that shows discoverability). It is also useful to say that citations are used as inputs for bibliometric studies.

Although citations correspond to an abstract concept, they are always identifiable within scientific text bodies. Zhuge (2016) points out that "explicit citations are the components of scientific papers and books" (see definition for citation components below).

Citation networks

Citations networks are formed by the conceptual links that connect different works through citations (citations connections) and makes them string attached among themselves in the backstage. "Citations knit together the whole world of scholarship into a gigantic citation network into a global endeavour, a directed graph with publications as the nodes and citations as the links between them, assigning credit to other researchers" (PERONI et al., p. 255; SHOTTON, 2018).

The connection between one work and another is explicit through citations. It not just about a matter of connections among works, but a matter of connections of the ideas and the contents these works stand for. That is to say that there is an implicit subject relationship established between the cited work and the citing work (WEB OF SCIENCE GROUP, 2019).

Citation networks provide data about the development of a scientific area, the role and level of scientific contribution for researchers, institutions and countries, and also, supports the estimating of the development of the areas, the decision on the possible directions a research might take and also, the impact assessment of a research (ZHUGE, 2016).

Different from static text, the citation network dynamically renders the source, the formation and evolution of a study, the backbone, the impact of researchers and institutions, potential knowledge flows through citation links [135], and the networks of cooperation between researchers and between institutions with the evolution of the area. Summaries of different scales can be obtained through zoom-in-and-zoom-out on the citation network. It is feasible to transform a citation network into a text by using some language patterns (for example, “the idea of A was extended by B,” “the idea of A was used by B,” and “the idea of A inspired B”) to represent different citations, main roles, relations, and development track (ZHUGE, 2016).

Figure 1 – Example of a citation network

Source: Santos; Martins; Karl, (2015).

Like other bibliographic analysis tools, citations networks may be constructed under different perspectives: by article, by author, by publisher and so on, according to the necessity of the researcher. That is to say that, there is infinity citations networks within the citation network that comprises the whole citations existing in the world.

Citation style

See bibliographic style.

Citing work

The work that contains a bibliographic reference to another work (PERONI et al., 2015, p. 257).

Cited work

The work that is being referred to by such a bibliographic reference (PERONI et al., 2015, p. 257).

Descriptive element

A word, phrase, or group of characters representing a distinct unit of information that forms part of an area of formal description (PEARCE-MOSES, 2005). Describing implies in the representation in written or in spoken language, of the object that is being described. Basically, this representation intends to detail every single characteristic of the described object. In a bibliographic context, a descriptive element corresponds to the smallest unit of information that comprises the description of a work or a publication be in a bibliographic record, be in a bibliographic reference (e.g., author, publication title, editor, year of publication, etc.).

Below follows the descriptive representations for the work "Alice in wonderland". The first one corresponds to a part of a bibliographic registry in Machine Readable Cataloging (MARC) format and the second, a bibliographic reference format. Each red box content represents a single descriptive element. A set of descriptive elements usually corresponds to the descriptive representation of the information. A descriptive element might be used in any information description tool, including bibliographic registers and bibliographic references.

Examples:

a) Bibliographic registry

00000970cam a22002771a 4500

0017805326

00520190731112101.0

008850926s1928 ilua 000 1 eng

1001_ |a **Carroll, Lewis,** |d **1832-1898.**

24510 |a **Alice's adventures in Wonderland /** |c by **Lewis Carroll;** **original Tenniel illustrations.**

260__ |a **Chicago :** |b **A. Whitman,** |c **1928.**

300__ |a **160 p. :** |b **ill. ;** |c **21 cm.**

4900_ |a **Just right book**

530__ |a **Also available in digital form.**

540__ |a **No known restrictions; no copyright renewal found,** Jul 24 2019

85641 | **<http://hdl.loc.gov/loc.gdc/scd0001.00025713291>**

b) bibliographic reference

LEWIS, C. *Alice's adventures in Wonderland.* Chicago: A. Whitman, 1928.

Document

Any kind of publication which is citable and also may be cited. This is not necessarily exclusively about works released by publishing companies (e.g. books, journals, dictionaries, encyclopaedias, etc.) but also includes materials published independently or non-officially published by an editorial group (e.g. preprints, datasets, academic works, blog posts, free software, etc.).

Editorial board

Group of experts in a journal's field which is responsible for determining the journal guidelines and for leading peer-review processes for the works submitted to the journal.

FRBR Entity

The entities represent the key objects of interest to users of a bibliographic data (IFLA, 2009, p. 13) and are defined as a "thing" or an "object" in the real world which may be uniquely identified in relation to all other objects and may be concrete or immaterial. The entities are complemented by the attributes, which indicates the characteristics of each type of entity, or descriptive properties of each member of a set of entities. An association between two or several entities corresponds to a relationship (CHEN, 1990).

As an entity-related concept model, all the FRBR entities are divided into three groups:

- a) First group (the products of intellectual production): work, expression, manifestation, item.
- b) Second group (the entities responsible for the physical production and dissemination, or the custodianship of the entities of the first group): person and corporate body.
- c) Third group (an additional set of entities that serve as the subjects of intellectual or artistic endeavour): concept, object, event, and place.

For the purposes of this glossary, only the definitions of the entities of the first group were considered and are strongly recommended to be consulted, although it's not an exhaustive definition. For the second and third groups entities definitions it is recommended the consult to the FRBR final report (IFLA, 2009) once it is not regarded to the scope of this glossary.

FRBR Expression

A conceptual definition that corresponds to "the intellectual or artistic realization of a work in the form of alpha-numeric, musical, or choreographic notation, sound, image, object, movement, etc., or any combination of such forms" (IFLA, 2009, p. 19). A work may take the form of text, sound, image, object, movement, etc., or any combination of such forms. Each form the work takes, independent of which one it is, corresponds to a single expression of a work. That is, a work may be realized through one or more than one expression, but an expression corresponds to only one work (IFLA, 2009, 2017) e.g., considering "Alice in Wonderland" as a work, each version of this is an expression: written (book), image (movie), sound (audiobook), object (sculpture), movement (play), etc.

The expression concept is integrant of the WEMI-Model (Work, Expression, Manifestation and Item model – see definition also in this glossary), which tries to identify the core aspects of publications and is the foundation of the FRBR family (IFLA, 2017).

Restricted access

Basically, restricted access publications are those whose access is opposite to open access. Restricted access means the online availability of metadata for academic and / or scientific content, whose full access is granted through a user's counterpart, which can be a registration, an individual or institutional subscription or any other form of payment for access or, access control validated by IP address.

Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records

See FRBR.

FRBR

FRBR (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records) is a complex conceptual entity-relationship model of the bibliographic universe, focused on the end-user, which was published in 1998 by the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) and corresponds to the development of basic requirements for an international standard bibliographic record (COYLE, 2016; TILLET, 2003). “This functional requirement emphasizes the importance of understanding the function of the data elements being recorded and how these elements each contribute to meeting user needs” (RIVA, 2007, p. 7).

“FRBR uses entity-relationship modelling, which is a standard technique, borrowed from Computer Science, used to analyse the structure of data prior to programming, particularly for database design. The modelling is independent of any specific program, code or standard” (RIVA, 2007, p. 8).

Also, the FRBR entity-relationship model provides a structure within which data requirements can be analysed in a systematic way and, a framework for analysing the uses that are made of bibliographic data considering each single entity, its relationships and attributes separately. This is useful not only for the task being performed by the user, but also to map the user tasks associated with the bibliographic resources described in catalogues, bibliographies, and other bibliographic tools they support, which can be four:

- a) to find entities that correspond to the user’s stated search criteria;
- b) to identify an entity;
- c) to select an entity;
- d) to acquire or obtain access to the entity described (IFLA, 2009, p. 79).

FRBR group 1 entities corresponds to the primary FRBR entities and their relationships which are illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2 - Many to many and one-to-many relationships in FRBR

Source: adapted from Coyle (2016) and Tillet (2003).

Each box of the figure represents an entity, that together composes the WEMI-Model (work, expression, manifestation, item – see definitions for all these entities also within this glossary). Each black arrow of the figure stands for a relationship between the entities, where one head indicates the possibility of establishing a single relationship, no exceptions admitted, and two heads indicates the possibility of establishing multiple relationships. That is to say that a work may be realized through one or more expressions. An expression may be embodied through one or more manifestations. A manifestation may be exemplified by one or more item. The

same logic is not completely applicable in the reverse way. An item exemplifies only one manifestation. A manifestation embodies only one expression. However, an expression “contains” only one work.

Manifestations may contain multiple expressions as indicated by the many-to-many relationship between expressions and manifestations. This is the only many-to-many relationship among the WEMI entities. A manifestation can embody multiple expressions and an expression can be embodied in multiple manifestations. By contrast, an expression can only realize a single work and an item can only exemplify a single manifestation (IFLA, 2016, p. 66).

On the other hand, the one-to-many relationship among manifestation and item entities means that a single manifestation may be exemplified in multiple items.

As already mentioned at the beginning of this definition, FRBR is a complex conceptual entity-relationship model and so, its definition is equally complex and would demand a long discussion that is not intended within the context of this glossary. For further and more detailed information about FRBR it is recommended the consult to the FRBR itself (see IFLA, 2009 bibliographic reference).

Issue

Each of the single edition published under the same volume of the same journal title.

Impact Factor (IF)

See Journal Impact Factor.

In-text reference pointer

The entity present in the body text of a citing work that denotes a particular bibliographic reference in the reference list or a footnote. In scientific literature, this in-text reference pointer can be presented in different forms – as a square-bracketed or superscripted number (e.g. “[3]” or “³”); as a square-bracketed text string comprising the first letter of each author’s surname (to a maximum of three) plus the last two digits of the publication year (e.g. “[RDS02]”); or as a parenthesised text string containing, for a single-author publication the author’s surname and the publication year (e.g. “(Renear, 2002)”), for a two-author publication both authors’ surnames and the publication year (e.g. “(Renear and Jones, 2002)”), or for a multi-author publication the first author’s surname followed by “et al.” and the publication year (e.g. “(Renear et al., 2002)”) (PERONI et al., 2015, p. 257).

In-text citation

The mention of a cited work content which is included within the text body of a citing work and followed by an in-text reference pointer that refers to a correspondent entry in the bibliographic references list. Unlike quotations, in-text citations reproduce fragments of the cited work content according to the interpretation of the author of the citing work, that is, in his own words.

Information

Probably the most challengeable definition of this glossary is this one: information. First, because of its conceptual meaning. Information cannot be “handled” or “measured”. It cannot be classified as important or irrelevant, since it strongly depends on the context it is applied for. So, exceptionally for this term, it will be used the reverse psychology fundamentals for understanding what information is not, prior to register any comment about its real definition in the context of this glossary.

Information is not knowledge. It is not intended to deepen the discussion on the conceptual distinctions between information and knowledge even because this is a topic widely explored in the literature. However, it is important to point that information is the most important input for knowledge construction and sharing. Information is valuable and difficult to manage. Valuable, because someone has given information a context, a meaning, an interpretation; someone reflected on knowledge, added to it his own wisdom, and considered its broader implications. Information also corresponds to the synthesis of multiple sources of information. Information is an object of difficult structuring and automated capture by machines. Generally, it is tacit (not expressed – work concept) and of difficult categorization, location, transfer and management (DAVENPORT, 1998). Information is cumulative, knowledge is selective (PESSOA, 2014).

Information is not formation. A formation implies a creation, a construction and the development of specific abilities for the development of an activity or an intellectual practice. These results generally are products of interaction between information and the prior knowledge of an individual.

Information is not power. And this is a polemic and questionable approach. Including, Pessoa (2014) refers to information as an indispensable source of power, that permits to change the facts and also the course of history. In this aspect, it is important to consider that: information may induce changes in an individual’s understanding and posture upon the fact (and this is a new fact itself), or the relationships between a person and a particular object. However, such changes are the result of the interpretation of all the information received by this person, from his own previous knowledge which is not exempt from beliefs, customs, social position and convictions. So actually, information is not a synonym of power, but foments decision making and attitudes which may configure an important element for reaching power.

Information is not the absolute truth. Instead, all information is subject to question and discussion and including, the empiricism is one of the characteristics of the scientific thinking. And that is precisely what allows knowledge advances in all knowledge areas. If it were not so, there would be no sense in developing studies and researches, events, publications and so on. Also, it is important to consider that Science has an endless approach, in the sense that a study is never conclusive and is subject to continuity (deepening included), questioning or even refutation. Facing this, the theoretical construct governing the human thought development is, in fact, the foundation that underpins Science, which reinforces the need for constant basal renewal and strengthening.

Information is not deformation. This statement inspires care by the double interpretation it may lead. Considering deformation as changing the original format of something, be it a habit or a thought, information assumes a positive character, considering that every process of changing demands the critical sense in order to conduct analysis and evaluations on possible directions for which such change may lead. The panorama is analogous to which refers to opinion formation. On the other hand, information assumes a negative character, considering deformation as a changing for the worse, what is perfectly possible, depending on the interpretation and use of the correct information, in the proper context.

Information is not a differential. Once more, the differential is not the information itself, but the product that may be generated by its influence.

Information is not decision making. On the other hand, any decision making may configure a negligence and culminate catastrophic results. It is evident that correct information combined with correct orientations in time and space favours risk reduction and increased security in decision making.

Information is not a data set. Assuming such statement as true may configure a simplistic, narrow and even dangerous argument that makes true and imminent the risk of arguing in a small way, especially with regard to semantic and terminological aspects. In this context, information may be characterized as an informal abstraction (that may not be formalized through a logical or mathematical theory), that is on somebody's mind, and represents some significant thing for this person (SETZER, 2015). The statement: "Paris is a fascinating city" is an example of information, as long as it is heard or read by someone, as long as "Paris" means the capital of France for this person (assuming the author wanted to refer to this city), and as long "fascinating" has the usual intuitive quality associated with that word.

Other approach correlates information to uncertainty (that is, the number of possible choices in order to create a message). The greater the freedom of choice, the greater the uncertainty, that is, the information. Under such an approach, the concept of information may seem disappointing and bizarre. Disappointing because it has nothing to do with the all meanings forementioned and bizarre, because it deals not with a unique message, but instead, with the statistic character of a set of messages, and also bizarre because in these statistic terms both terms information and uncertainty are partners (SHANNON; WEAVER, 1972, apud CAPURRO, 2007).

The irony of total immersion in information and the central role it plays in our economic, social and cultural life is that most of the time we do not have a clear understanding of what exactly information is. Information is not a simple and straightforward concept, but a very slippery notion, used in many different ways. Linguistically and grammatically, the word information is a noun, but actually describes a process and therefore is like a verb (LOGAN, 2012).

And what's most curious about it is that in the end information is not a phenomenon, nor a concept, nor a property. Information is not knowledge, nor a formation, nor power, nor absolute truth, nor deformation. And in the end, information is all, and supports all, even being nothing and supporting nothing. It all depends on the point of view.

Information is a multi-semantic term which can be applied in many contexts and because of that, constructing a precise and global definition for this term is challenger. So, for the specific purposes of this glossary, information will be considered as the registry of the representation of knowledge. That is to say that a work contains information that represents the author's knowledge.

FRBR Item

The entity defined as item is a concrete entity. It is in many instances a single physical object (e.g., a copy of a one-volume monograph, a single audio cassette, etc.). There are instances, however, where the entity defined as item comprises more than one physical object (e.g., a monograph issued as two separately bound volumes, a recording issued on three separate compact discs, etc.) (IFLA, 2009, p. 24).

In terms of intellectual content and physical form, an item exemplifying a manifestation is normally the same as the manifestation itself. However, variations may occur from one item to another, even when the items exemplify the same manifestation, where those variations are the result of actions external to the intent of the producer of the manifestation (e.g., damage occurring after the item was produced, binding performed by a library, etc.) (IFLA, 2009, p. 24).

The item concept is integrant of the WEMI-Model (Work, Expression, Manifestation and Item model – see definition also in this glossary), which tries to identify the core aspects of publications and is the foundation of the FRBR family (IFLA, 2017).

Journal

A journal is a type of a periodical (see definition ahead) that corresponds to the serial and continuous scholarly publication under the same title released in regular time intervals for unlimited period, which contains articles written by researchers, professors and other experts intended for an academic or technical audience. Generally, a journal is identified by an ISSN number and each issue is identified by a consecutive number, and besides, is focused on a specific discipline or subject area (CUNHA, CAVALCANTE, 2008, p. 279).

Journal Impact factor (IF)

The Journal Impact Factor is a scientometric index which was developed in 1961 by Eugene Garfield and is defined as the total number of citations received by a specific journal indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection in the previous two years, divided by the total number of citable works (that comprise articles, reviews, and proceedings papers) published by that journal in the same period. Although the citing works may be articles published in the same evaluated journal, most of them are from different journals, proceedings, or books indexed in Web of Science Core Collection. A Journal Impact Factor of 1.0 means that, on average, the articles published one or two years ago have been cited one time. A Journal Impact Factor of 2.5 means that, on average, the articles published one or two years ago have been cited two and a half times (CLARIVATE ANALYTICS, 2019; WIKIPEDIA, 2019). Even not being an exact mathematical average, the Journal Impact Factor provides a functional approximation of the mean citation rate per citable item (CLARIVATE ANALYTICS, 2019) but, however, its use has been criticized and considered as a reductive and dangerous metric. It has also been pointed that “Journals do not calculate their impact factor directly — it is calculated and published by Thomson Reuters” (TIME..., 2016). “Journal Impact Factors were designed to indicate the quality of journals, but researchers often use the metrics to assess the quality of individual papers — and even, in some cases, their authors” (CALLAWAY, 2016). It has also being stated that although impact factor has been developed with the specific purpose to measure the impact of scientific journals it has lately been used for measuring the quality of scientific journals, individual journals and even of individual researchers and to evaluate grant applications and other financial supports to research programs. Because of that, the impact factor has been considered as an unreliable instrument for measuring the quality of journals what may cause unfairness (EASE, 2007).

List of references

See bibliographic references list.

Link rot

Hyperlinks that points to a website, a server or any other source that is no longer available through that link.

Long quotation

See block quotation

FRBR Manifestation

“The physical embodiment of an expression of a work” (IFLA, 2009, p. 21).

The entity defined as manifestation encompasses a wide range of materials, including manuscripts, books, periodicals, maps, posters, sound recordings, films, video recordings, CD-ROMs, multimedia kits, etc. As an entity, manifestation represents all the physical objects that bear the same characteristics, in respect to both intellectual content and physical form (IFLA, 2009, p. 21).

When a work is realized, the resulting expression of the work may be physically embodied on or in a medium such as paper, audio tape, video tape, canvas, plaster, etc. That physical embodiment constitutes a manifestation of the work. In some cases, there may be only a single physical exemplar produced of that manifestation of the work (e.g., an author’s manuscript, a tape recorded for an oral history archive, an original oil painting, etc.). In other cases, there are multiple copies produced in order to facilitate public dissemination or distribution. In those cases, there is normally a more formal production process involved, and a publisher, takes responsibility for the process. In other cases there may be only a limited number of copies made of an original exemplar for purposes such as private study (e.g., a dubbing of an original recording of a piece of music), or preservation (e.g., a photocopy produced on permanent paper of an author’s original typescript) (IFLA, 2009, p. 21-22).

The manifestation concept is integrant of the WEMI-Model (Work, Expression, Manifestation and Item model – see definition also in this glossary), which tries to identify the core aspects of publications and is the foundation of the FRBR family (IFLA, 2017).

A manifestation represents all the physical objects that bear the same characteristics of intellectual content and physical form. In actuality, a manifestation is itself an immaterial entity, but describes and represents physical entities, that is all the items that have the same content and carrier. So writing a bibliographic record of this work (cataloguing), is the same as describing the manifestation and this bibliographic record may be shared with other libraries (or information units) which also own a copy of the same manifestation (TILLET, 2003).

Mention

The reproduction of the idea of a cited work under the interpretation and on the own words of the author of a citing work. Although do not require a graphic highlight in the text body like indents or quotes, mentions also must create a citation, considering it demands a indication of an in-text reference pointer and its respective bibliographic reference that must appear in the bibliographic references list.

Original communication

An original communication is a specific kind of article which contains the discussion and the unpublished results of a research.

Periodical

A publication that corresponds to the serial and continuous scholarly publication under the same title released in regular time intervals for unlimited period (CUNHA, CAVALCANTE, 2008)

Publication

A work, which may be edited or not, offered to the public with the consent of the author or of the copyright holder by any way or process (CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008).

Publisher

An individual or organization that produces and markets creative works for distribution (PEARCE-MOSES, 2005). The entity responsible for publishing works. In some cases the publisher may be a company of the editorial branch, in other cases it may be the author himself.

Quartile

Based on Impact Factor (IF) data, the Journal Citation Reports published by Thomson Reuters provides yearly rankings of science and social science journals, in the subject categories relevant for the journal (in fact, there may be more than one). Quartile rankings are derived for each journal in each of its subject categories according to which quartile of the impact factor distribution the journal occupies for that subject category. Q1 denotes the top 25% of the impact factor distribution, Q2 for middle-high position (between top 50% and top 25%), Q3 middle-low position (top 75% to top 50%), and Q4 the lowest position (bottom 25% of the impact factor distribution)

Unfortunately, papers cannot be easily associated to a single ISI subject category (at least, not always), and one has therefore to consider the full range of quartile rankings of the journal. Following this line, a quartile score (indeed, a discrete distribution) is associated to any paper published in IF-ranked journals by uniformly distributing a unitary mass over the quartile rankings of the journal in which the paper was published (for that year) (FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER, c2012).

Quotation

A quotation results from the act of quoting and corresponds to an exact transcription (copy, reproduction) of part of an external cited work (even published or not) within the text body of the citing work. Any way of expressing the knowledge may be quoted, what means that not only written works may be quoted but also, speeches, music, images and any other way of representing and expressing information. Quotations are more commonly used in scientific texts for grounding an argumentation, but they also may be useful to present counterpoints, questions, confirmations, agreements, contradictions and complements. Quotations may also be classified into block quotations and run-in quotations. See definitions separately for more details.

Quotation marks

Quotation marks are punctuation signals (""") put in the beginning and in the end of run-in quotations to delimit the specific length of the transcription of a cited work.

Quotes

See quotation marks

Quote marks

See quotation marks

Reference

the word “reference” is colloquially used to mean many things: either the bibliographic reference itself, or the entry in the body text of an article that denotes such a reference, or the act of citing the target publication, or the actual target publication itself (as in “Have you read that reference yet?”). The word also has variety of other meanings, and in particular is widely used in academia to mean a statement about a person’s achievements, qualifications, competence and character, supplied, for example, in support of a job application or an academic promotion (PERONI, et al., 2015, p. 255).

The concept of reference is something broad. In the most general context, the most common definition of reference is the act of providing complimentary information by mentioning another instance (someone or something). Generally, a reference occurs by indicating an object, a person, a place or anything else in a concrete or in an abstract sphere, by means of a sign, a word, a number or any other means of representing the indicated object (e.g., during his speech, the director will refer to different branches of acting. The professor told the students to do the exercises she referred to in the last class).

In a very general scientific approach, the concept of reference regards to a practice to lead the reader to specific complimentary information. In a more accurate view, references may assume various significances, from which two are particularly related to the scientific sphere:

- a) Reference as a mention instance: a way to refer the reader to a specific piece of information, which may be within the text itself or in an external source of information. One of the functions of referencing in scientific context is to offer the reader the opportunity to be provided with more accurate, complimentary or related information about a topic. It is quite useful to elucidate or substantiate a discourse, or for adding detailed data about something. In these cases, the author needs to mention other instances, which may be a publication, a place, another specific part of his own text... etc., in order to include, complement, or simply to registry the existence of an information source, or other specific issue (e.g. Aspirin is a Nonsteroidal Anti-inflammatory Drug indicated to relieve pain, fever, and inflammation (find complimentary information about this and other drugs and chemicals at PubChem database); or: “this issue will be discussed on chapter 5”). It is also true that sometimes a reference demands the indication of a bibliographic reference regarding to it in the bibliographic references list;
- b) reference as a pointer instance: reference also may be applied in scientific works to indicate the origin (source) of an information. For example, when an author reproduces someone else’s ideas in his own work, the proper way of informing the reader that that specific piece of information is not his authorship is using a reference to the original source of that specific information. This specific single information identifier, which is called in-text reference pointer, is also a reference, since it makes reference to other information e.g., “Computational ontologies are a means to

formally model the structure of a system, i.e., the relevant entities and relations that emerge from its observation, and which are useful to our purposes” (GUARINO; OBERLE; STAAB, 2009, p. 2). It is important to point out that the reference is only the piece of information contained between the parentheses, which indicate the metadata for the reader to find more information about the publication mentioned (cited) at the bibliographic references list at the end of the publication, that is, the author’s surnames, the date of the publication and the pages where the cited excerpt may be found.

Still considering references as a pointer instance, it is proper to say that they can also be used to indicate graphics or figures within the text body, web links, annexes, appendices, glossaries, indexes, tables, a notation for a footnote, and any other element which the author considers may be of interest to the reader (e.g., “the compilation of the data gathered from the analysis may be consulted in annex 2”, or “the graphic 1 shows the distribution of the population, by age”).

At last, considering that the term “reference” has multiple definitions with multiple interpretations and uses, it is useful to remember that a work may comprises lots or references, in-text pointers and bibliographic references included.

For the purposes of this work, the terminological approach that will be considered for the term reference is an indication that forwards the reader to a specific excerpt in the text itself or to other information sources regarding to a subject (CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008).

Reference management software

Dedicated application to automatically organize, manage and format bibliographic references into different bibliographic styles, according to the options selected by the user. Zotero, EndNote (and Endnote Web), Mendeley, Papers and Refworks are some examples of reference management software.

Run-in quotation (simple run-in quotation)

A Run-in quotation, also called simple run-in quotation, is a textual quotation that is included inline and is usually enclosed within quotation marks. (SHOTTON, PERONI, 2015). The length limit for a quotation to be classified as a run-in quotation or as a block quotation is determined by the bibliographic style in use.

Standard

Set of established rules resulted from a particular normalization effort which, after being approved by an established institution, takes the format of a document containing a set of requirements to be attended in order to establish specific conditions to the realization of an activity as well as provide a background for the establishment of derived standards (CUNHA; CAVALCANTI, 2008).

Style manual

See bibliographic style.

Subject category

A topic subdivision of a general area of Science according to the context of the catalog or database it is applied in (CLARIVATE ANALYTICS, 2019?).

FRBR Work

Work is a conceptual entity that stands for the mental or artistic activity from which results the product of the intellectual or artistic creation. And as an abstract concept, a work is neither physical nor palpable. That is to say that its “formal existence” is necessarily conditioned to the registration in a physical or digital support. Therefore, a work becomes factibile through “individual realizations or expressions of the work, but the work itself exists only in the commonality of content between and among the various expressions of the work” (IFLA, 1997, p. 17). The materialization of a work occurs through its expression that can occur in many ways: written, spoken, sung, painted or converted into works of art, as in the case of sculptures, and other forms of intellectual production. These expressions must be embodied in one or more manifestation, that is, it must be registered in a physical or digital support to make possible its management and retrieval. Usually these embodiments also are exemplified in various items, so that it may be distributed in the most convenient form according to the context and other interests, including the editorial ones.

The work concept is integrant of the WEMI-Model (Work, Expression, Manifestation and Item model – see definition also in this glossary), which tries to identify the core aspects of publications and is the foundation of the FRBR family (IFLA, 2017).

REFERENCES

ABNT. **ABNT NBR 6023**: Informação e documentação: referências: elaboração. Rio de Janeiro: ABNT, 2018.

CALLAWAY, E. Publising elite turns against impact factor: senior staff at societies and leading journals want to end inappropriate use of the measure. **Nature**, London, v. 535, n. 7611, p. 210-211, Jul. 2016. Available at https://www.nature.com/news/polopoly_fs/1.20224!/menu/main/topColumns/topLeftColumn/pdf/nature.2016.20224.pdf. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

CHEN, P. **Modelagem de dados**: a abordagem entidade-relacionamento para projeto lógico. São Paulo: Mcgraw Hill, 1990.

CLARIVATE ANALYTICS. **InCites Journal Citation Reports Help**. [S./]: Clarivate Analytics, 2019?. Available in: <http://help.incites.clarivate.com/incitesLiveJCR/glossaryAZgroup/g8/4346-TRS.html>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

COYLE, K. **FRBR before and after**: a look a tour bibliographic models. Chicago, ALA editions, 2016. Available at <http://kcoyle.net/beforeAndAfter/978-0-8389-1364-2.pdf>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

CUNHA, M. B. da.; CAVALCANTI, C. R. de O. **Dicionário de Biblioteconomia e Arquivologia**. Brasília, DF: Briquet de Lemos, 2008.

DAVENPORT, T. H. **A ecologia da informação**. São Paulo: Futura, 1998.

EASE. EASE statement on inappropriate use of impact factors. [S./]: EASE, 2007. Available at https://ease.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/ease_statement_ifs_final.pdf. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER. **Journal citation ranking and quartile scores**. Trento, Fondazione Bruno Kessler, c2012. Available at https://researchassessment.fbk.eu/quartile_score. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

ISO. **ISO 690**: information and documentation: guidelines for bibliographic references and citations to information resources. ISO: Geneva, 2010.

GUERNSEY, L. Cyberspace citations: scholars debate how best to cite research conducted on the Internet. **The Chronicle of Higher Education**, Washington, DC, v. 42, n. 18, p. A18-A21, Jan. 1996.

GUO, Z. **Knowledge discovery from citation networks**. [S.l.: s.n., ca. 2010]. Available at http://www.cs.binghamton.edu/~zguo/paper/dm917_guo.pdf. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

IFLA. **Functional requirements for bibliographic records**. [S.l.]: IFLA, 2009. Available at https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/cataloguing/frbr/frbr_2008.pdf. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

IFLA. **Functional requirements for bibliographic records (FRBR)**. 2017. Available at <https://www.ifla.org/best-practice-for-national-bibliographic-agencies-in-a-digital-age/node/8915>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

IFLA. **FRBR-Library reference model**. Den Haag: IFLA, 2016. Available at: https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/cataloguing/frbr-lrm/frbr-lrm_20160225.pdf. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

LANNING, S. A modern, simplified citation style and student response. **Reference Services Review**, London, v. 44, n. 1, p. 21-37, 2016.

LOGAN, R. K. **Que é informação?**: a propagação da organização na biosfera, na simbolosfera, na tecnosfera e na econosfera. Tradução Adriana Braga. Rio de Janeiro: Contraponto : PUC-Rio, 2012.

NAUMIS PEÑA, C. Registro bibliográfico y referencia bibliográfica: una revisión conceptual. **Revista Interamericana de Bibliotecología**, Medelín, v. 31, n. 1, p. 227-245, ene./jun. 2008. Available at <https://aprendeenlinea.udea.edu.co/revistas/index.php/RIB/article/download/1925/1586>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

NAUMIS PEÑA, Catalina. Ene.-Jun. 2008, vol. 31, no. 1, p. 227-245.

NORDQUIST, R. **How to use block quotations in writing**. 2019. Available at <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-block-quotation-1689173>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

PEARCE-MOSES, R. **A glossary of archival and records terminology**. Chicago: The Society of American Archivists, 2005. (Archival fundamentals series. II). Available at <http://files.archivists.org/pubs/free/SAA-Glossary-2005.pdf>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

PERONI, S. et al. Setting our bibliographic references free: towards open citation data. **Journal of Documentation**, London, v. 71, n. 2, p. 253-277, 2015.

PESSOA, C. **Informação não é conhecimento**. [S.l.: s.n.], 2014. Available at <http://www.carlospessoa.com.br/artigo/informacao-nao-e-conhecimento-2/>. Last accessed: 18 August 2017

RIVA, P. Introducing the Funcional Requirements for Bibliographic Records and related IFLA developments. **Bulletin of the American Society for Information Science and Technology**, Maryland, v. 36, n. 6, p. 7-11, 2007. Available at

<https://asistdl.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/bult.2007.1720330604>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

SANTOS, J. C.; MARTINS, F. V.; KARL, H. B. Different perspectives on internationalization research: a bibliometric review. **Revista Ibero-Americana de Estratégia**, São Paulo, v. 14, n. 4, p. 93-118, out./dez. 2015. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/304420569_Different_Perspectives_on_Internationalization_Research_A_Bibliometric_Review. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

SETZER, V. W. **Dado, informação, conhecimento e competência**. [São Paulo], 2015. Available at <https://www.ime.usp.br/~vwsetzer/dado-info.html>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

SHANNON, C.; WEAVER, W. The mathematical theory of communication. Urbana: University of Illinois Press, 1972. Apud CAPURRO R.; HJORLAND, B. O conceito de informação. Rio de Janeiro, **Perspectivas em Ciência da Informação**, Belo Horizonte, v. 12, n. 1, p. 148-207, jan./abr. 2007. Available at <http://portaldeperiodicos.eci.ufmg.br/index.php/pci/article/view/54/47>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

SHOTTON, D. Funders should mandate open citations. **Nature**, London, v. 553, p. 129, Jan. 2018. Available at <https://www.nature.com/magazine-assets/d41586-018-00104-7/d41586-018-00104-7.pdf>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

SHOTTON, D.; PERONI, S. **DoCo, the document components ontology**. [S.l.: s.n.], 2015. Available at <https://sparontologies.github.io/doco/current/doco.html#d4e382>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

TILLET, B. **The FRBR model**: (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records). San Jose, CA: April 4-5, 2003. ALCTS Institute on Metadata and AACR2. Available at <https://www.loc.gov/catdir/cpso/frbrengr.pdf>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

TIME to remodel the journal impact factor. **Nature**, London, v. 535, n. 7613, p. 466, July 2016. Available at <https://www.nature.com/articles/535466a.pdf>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

THE UNIVERSITY OF NOTTINGHAM. **What are bibliographies and references?**. United Kingdom: University of Nottingham, [2019?]. Available at <https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/studentsservices/documents/whatarebibliographiesandreferences.pdf>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

WEB OF SCIENCE GROUP. **Backward and forward citations**. [S.l.]: Web of Science Group, 2019. Available at: <https://clarivate.libguides.com/woscc/citationnetwork>. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

WIKIPEDIA. **Impact factor**. [S.l.]: Wikipedia, 2019. Available at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Impact_factor#cite_note-garfield-4. Last accessed: 23 August 2020

ZHUGE, H. General Citation. In: ZHUGE, H. **Multi-dimensional summarization in cyber-physical society**. Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2016. Chapter 8. p. 107-114. (Computer Science Reviews and Trends).